

Aluminium incorporation in TiO₂ rutile at high pressure.

A XRD and high-resolution ²⁷Al NMR study.

Alberto Escudero,^{1} Laurent Delevoye,² Falko Langenhorst¹*

¹Bayerisches Geoinstitut, Universität Bayreuth, D-95440 Bayreuth, Germany

²Unité de Catalyse et de Chimie du Solide (UMR CNRS 8181), Université Lille Nord de France, F-59652 Villeneuve d'Ascq, France.

Alberto.Escudero@uni-bayreuth.de aescudero@icmse.csic.es

Corresponding author. Phone + 49 - 921-553839, Fax +49 - 921 55-3769; e-mail address: Alberto.Escudero@uni-bayreuth.de. Present address: Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Sevilla, Spain. E-mail address: aescudero@icmse.csic.es

ABSTRACT: Aluminium incorporation into rutile (TiO₂) at high pressure and high temperature has been studied by XRD as well as high resolution ²⁷Al MAS – NMR, MQ-MAS-NMR. High pressure enhances the Al solubility into TiO₂ rutile, which is able to incorporate up to at least 5 weight % Al₂O₃ at 5.5 GPa. Up to four aluminium environments in octahedral coordination in rutile have been observed. The main mechanism of solubility at low pressure is the substitution of Ti⁴⁺ by Al³⁺ on normal octahedral sites, but aluminium also occupies octahedral interstices of rutile, especially at higher pressures. The assignation of the NMR signals corresponding to interstitial Al and substitutional Al associated with an interstitial Al in the rutile structure has been carried out from the combination of both XRD and NMR data and the relative higher importance of both environments at high pressure. The

increase of the population of interstitial octahedral aluminium with increasing pressure gives rise to the reduction of symmetry in rutile from tetragonal to orthorhombic.

KEYWORDS: Rutile; alumina; solid solutions; high pressure experiments; ^{27}Al NMR spectroscopy.

BRIEFS: Aluminium solubility in rutile increases at high pressure. Two different mechanisms for aluminium incorporation in rutile: substitutional and interstitial solid solutions. High pressure induces the incorporation of interstitial aluminium, which causes a decrease of the rutile symmetry from a tetragonal structure to an orthorhombic.

MANUSCRIPT TEXT

1. Introduction

Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) has been intensively studied because of both basic and applied interests in material science and geosciences. TiO_2 is a polymorphous compound, crystallizing at atmospheric pressure as rutile, anatase, or brookite. All of them have the same fundamental structural octahedral units with different arrangements.¹ Due to their photoconductive and catalyst characteristics, TiO_2 polymorphs are, for example, widely used in industrial applications, i.e. for hydrogen production² and UV-induced oxidation of organic compounds in wastewater³ and also as a white pigment. The photocatalyst properties of TiO_2 can be modified by introducing small amounts of impurities into its structure.⁴ Indeed, many studies about both the metal and non-metal doping of TiO_2 appear in the recent literature.⁵⁻¹² The incorporation of Al into rutile has been widely studied at atmospheric pressure.^{13,14,15,16} The introduction of Al in rutile reduces its photoactivity and prevents the degradation of paints and other coatings by forming oxygen vacancies that can trap charge carriers.¹⁷ From the experimental point of view, the active magnetic character of ^{27}Al allows the study of its incorporation into TiO_2 by NMR. However, the influence of pressure on the solubility and incorporation mechanism of Al in TiO_2 is so far unexplored. On one hand, high-pressure research is recently leading to the identification of new types of physical behaviour and new families of potential technological materials,

often with previously unknown structure types and chemical and physical properties.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ On the other hand, basic knowledge of the effect of pressure on the incorporation and solubility of trace elements (e.g. Fe, Al, Zr, Nb) is also important for geoscientific studies because rutile is a common and widespread accessory mineral in high-pressure rocks from the deeper crust and Earth's mantle. The trace element geochemistry of rutile provides thereby useful information on provenance,²⁰ temperature and pressure,²¹ and ages of host rocks.²² In this study, we have carried out high-pressure piston cylinder and multi-anvil experiments on rutile that address the effect of the pressure on the structure of Al – doped rutile and allow describing the mechanism for the Al incorporation in rutile.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Synthesis

A mixture with a 95% TiO₂ + 5% Al₂O₃ (weight %) composition was prepared from TiO₂ (rutile nanopowder, 99.5% Sigma) and Al₂O₃ (corundum nanopowder, 99.97%, Chempur). The oxides were mixed in a ball mill at 600 rpm during 60 minutes. This precursor material was later subjected to high pressure at 1 and 3 GPa in an end-loaded piston-cylinder. Samples were placed in a Pt capsule and inserted into a ½” talc/pyrex assemblage. Temperature was controlled by using a Pt₉₀Rh₁₀ -Pt thermocouple. Samples were first pressurized to the peak pressure and then heated at 1300°C for 24 hours. Temperature was immediately quenched and the samples were decompressed until atmospheric pressure in 20 minutes.

The same precursor material was also treated at 5.5 GPa in a 1200 tonne MA8 Kawai-type multi-anvil press, using 25 mm Cr₂O₃-doped MgO octahedra and a stepped LaCrO₃ furnace. The high pressure octahedral assembly was compressed using 8 tungsten carbide anvils with corner truncations of 15 mm lengths. Sample was placed in a Pt metal foil capsule and inserted into the centre of the furnace inside an MgO sleeve. All ceramic parts of the high pressure cell were fired at 1000°C for 30 minutes prior to assembling. A W₉₇Re₃ -W₇₅Re₂₅ thermocouple was inserted to measure the temperature at the top

surface of the capsule. The sample was first pressurized to the target pressure and then heated at 1600°C for 15 minutes. Temperature was immediately quenched and the samples were decompressed until atmospheric pressure in 16 hours. Piston cylinder sample weights were about 200 mg whereas about 40 mg of final product was obtained after the multi-anvil synthesis.

A second precursor material with a 99.3 % TiO₂ + 0.7% Al₂O₃ (weight %) composition was annealed at 1500°C at atmospheric pressure for two days.

2.2 Characterization

The quenched samples were analysed at atmospheric pressure by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a Stoe STADI-P diffractometer operating in transmission mode, using Co K α 1 radiation selected with a focusing germanium monochromator and a linear position-sensitive detector. The patterns were recorded from $2\theta = 20^\circ$ to 120° with 0.016° steps and 1000 s counting time. The LeBail algorithm of the program package GSAS²³ was used to determine unit cell parameters. Refined parameters were background coefficients, unit cell parameters, line widths, asymmetry parameters and zero error.

²⁷Al triple and single quantum - magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance (3Q MQ MAS and MAS - NMR) spectroscopy experiments were carried out in a Bruker DRX800 (18.8 T) spectrometer installed at the University of Lille, France. The spectrometer is equipped with a multinuclear probe operating at 208.49 MHz for ²⁷Al. Powdered samples were packed in 2.5 mm zirconia rotors and spun at 30 kHz. The ²⁷Al 3Q MQMAS²⁴⁻²⁵ NMR experiments were performed using a Z-filtered pulse sequence,²⁶ composed of three pulses. Excitation and mixing were done at radiofrequency field strength of 125 kHz in order to increase the efficiency of the MQ experiment. The pulse lengths were experimentally optimized and their respective durations were 4.5 and 1.5 μ s. The duration of the last selective $\pi/2$ pulse was 8 μ s, being the recycle delay of 1 s. In order to avoid sidebands in the indirect dimension, the t_1 time increment was set to the rotor period of 33.3 μ s (corresponding to MAS rate of 30 kHz)²⁷, and typically 90 t_1 increments were needed. For the single pulse MAS – NMR experiment a

pulse width of 0.5 μs ($\pi/2$ pulse length of 5 μs) was used. The delay time was optimized to 500 ms. The chemical shifts are reported in ppm from 0.1 M AlCl_3 solution.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 X-ray Diffraction data

Figure 1 shows the XRD diagrams of the 5% Al_2O_3 samples synthesised at 1 and 3 GPa and 1300°C and 5.5 GPa and 1600°C. The diagram corresponding to the 0.7 % Al_2O_3 sample synthesised at 1500°C at atmospheric pressure has also been added to the figure for comparative reasons. All the diagrams show reflections corresponding to rutile (PDF 21-1276). Some very small signals at $2\theta = 40.7^\circ$ and 50.7° are observed in the samples synthesised at 1 and 3 GPa (Figures 1b and c). These reflections correspond to $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, corundum (PDF 10-173) and have slightly more intensity in the 1 GPa sample. No signals corresponding to $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, corundum, are observed in the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa. However, a careful inspection of the diagrams of the samples synthesised at 3 and 5.5 GPa (Figures 1c and d) reveals a splitting of rutile (101), $2\theta = 42.2^\circ$, (200), $2\theta = 45.8^\circ$, (210), $2\theta = 51.6^\circ$ and (211), $2\theta = 64.0^\circ$ reflections, marked with asterisks in Figure 1, while the ones corresponding to (110), $2\theta = 32.0$ and (111), $2\theta = 48.3^\circ$ remain unchanged. This indicates a lowering of symmetry of the rutile structure, which apparently transforms from a tetragonal to an orthorhombic structure between 1 and 3 GPa at 1300°C. On the basis of the systematic absences, the XRD patterns of the samples synthesised at 3 and 5.5 GPa are compatible with an orthorhombic unit cell with possible space groups $Pnmm$ or $Pnn2$.

The XRD patterns of the samples have been analysed with the Le Bail method using the GSAS software,²³ as described in the experimental section. The starting parameters have been taken from Bokhimi, Morales and Pedraza for pure rutile.²⁸ The very small reflections corresponding to Al_2O_3 corundum were removed previously to the fit, when present. All the remaining reflections of the samples synthesised at atmospheric pressure and 1 GPa could be fitted on the basis of a tetragonal unit

cell with space group $P4_2/mnm$, which is the one corresponding to TiO_2 rutile. The orthorhombic space group $Pnmm$ was used to fit the patterns of the 3 and 5.5 GPa samples. The GSAS fitted curve and the difference curve obtained from the Le Bail refinement of the XRD diagram of the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa and 1600°C are shown in Figure 2. For the orthorhombic samples, the $Pnmm$ space group has been used in the refinement, but the same results are obtained when using the $Pnn2$. The lattice parameters of the different samples are shown in table 1.

Two types of mechanisms for the Al incorporation in TiO_2 rutile at atmospheric pressure have been reported in the literature.^{13, 15, 29} One of them consists of the substitution of Ti^{4+} by Al^{3+} on normal octahedral sites, compensating the lower cationic charge with oxygen vacancies. The other mechanism consists of the incorporation of Al^{3+} into unoccupied interstitial sites of the rutile structure. Two types of vacant interstitial sites could accommodate extra cations in the rutile structure: $0 \frac{1}{2} 0$ octahedral positions and $0 \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{4}$ tetrahedral sites. In both cases, there are four sites per unit cell.¹³ Since the interstices with octahedral geometry are distorted, there are two sets of distances between the centre of the octahedron and the oxygens. Four oxygens are at a distance of 2.22 Å, while the two others are at a distance of 1.66 Å along the $[3\bar{2}0]$ direction, which is the tie line along the two closest oxygens of the octahedron. In the case of the tetrahedral interstices, there is a common distance from the centre of the tetrahedron to the oxygens of 1.81 Å. Taking into account an average Al – O distance in octahedral coordination between 1.85 and 1.98 Å, the distances found in corundum ($\alpha - Al_2O_3$),³⁰ and an average Al – O distance of 1.76 Å in tetrahedral coordination,³¹ the Al^{3+} entering into the tetrahedral interstices would not cause an appreciable distortion. However, the incorporation of Al^{3+} into the octahedral interstices would expand the lattice in the $[3\bar{2}0]$ direction, giving rise to a reduction of rutile symmetry from tetragonal to orthorhombic. Thus, the incorporation of Al^{3+} into the $0 \frac{1}{2} 0$ octahedral interstices of rutile is likely to be responsible of the orthorhombic distortion observed in rutile. However, the presence of tetrahedral aluminium cannot be discarded on the basis on the XRD data.

3.2 ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectroscopy

Triple-quantum ^{27}Al MAS-NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at 3 GPa and 1300°C and at 5.5 GPa and 1600°C were carried out to remove the largest part of the quadrupolar interactions for a better identification of the different Al environments. The MQMAS experiment yields a two-dimensional spectrum that has both a triple-quantum dimension (F1 dimension) and a single-quantum MAS dimension (F2 dimension). MQMAS NMR experiments thereby allow remarkable enhancements in resolution over single pulse MAS experiments. The MQMAS NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at 3 GPa and 1300°C and 5.5 GPa and 1600°C are shown in Figure 3. The corresponding F1 dimensions of the 3QMAS-NMR spectra are shown in Figure 4. Several signals in the typical range for octahedral Al can be observed in both spectra. Except for the signal corresponding to corundum, centred at 16 ppm and present in the spectra of the sample synthesised at 3 GPa (Figures 3I and 4a), both spectra show the same number of peaks. The absence of the crossing signal corresponding to corundum in the MQMAS spectrum of the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa and 1600°C (Figure 3II) indicates that all the Al has been incorporated into the TiO_2 structure and no rests of Al_2O_3 are present in this sample, as indicated by the XRD data. The signals differ in the relative intensity and slightly in the position. The F1-projection of the triple-quantum ^{27}Al MAS-NMR spectrum corresponding to the sample synthesised at 3 GPa consists of three signals and a possible shoulder situated at -3.6, 0.1, 2.9 and 6.1 ppm, respectively. They have been labelled A, B, C and D, respectively. The maxima of the peaks corresponding to the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa (Figure 4b) are situated at -2.3, 0.8, 2.9 and 7.6 ppm. Due to the high external magnetic field (18.8 T) and taking into account that the electric field gradients are normally not very intense for octahedral Al, each peak corresponds very likely to a different Al environment. Thus, NMR data indicate the presence of at least four different octahedral Al environments in Al-doped TiO_2 rutile at high pressure.

Figure 5 shows the single pulse ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at 1, 3 and 5.5 GPa. The spectrum corresponding to the 99.3% TiO_2 + 0.7% Al_2O_3 calcined at 1500°C at atmospheric pressure (Figure 5a) has been added to the figure for comparative reasons. This spectrum shows a

narrow signal centred at about -5.9 ppm, a possible signal at about -1.9 ppm and a broad band centred at c.a. 10 ppm, being similar to the spectra reported by Stebbins for Al-doped rutile at atmospheric pressure.¹⁴ The signals are compatible with the A, B and D peaks observed previously in the 3QMAS-NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at high pressure, respectively. A peak centred at 15 ppm and corresponding to Al₂O₃ corundum appears in the spectra of the samples synthesised at 1 and 3 GPa (Figures 5b and c), as expected from the XRD data. Its intensity decreases with increasing pressure, demonstrating that the incorporation of Al into TiO₂ rutile increases with increasing pressure. According to the ²⁷Al 3Q-MAS-NMR spectrum, there is no rest of corundum in the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa. This indicates that the small band centred at c.a. 14 ppm in its single pulse ²⁷Al MAS-NMR spectrum (Figure 5d) should correspond to the previously labelled D signal on the ²⁷Al 3Q-MAS-NMR spectrum. This contribution is only visible in the MAS spectrum of the 5.5 GPa sample and resembles the broad band observed in the sample calcined at atmospheric pressure. The rest of the signals observed in the ²⁷Al 3Q-MAS-NMR spectra (A, B and C) can also be distinguished on the MAS spectra. The position of the A signal shifts slightly toward higher frequencies when increasing the synthesis pressure and even appears as a shoulder of the B signal in the spectrum of the 5.5 GPa sample. A small and broad band centred at about 57 ppm also appears in the MAS spectra. A higher magnification of the spectrum corresponding to the sample synthesised at 3 GPa has been added to Figure 5. This band can be attributed to tetrahedral Al.

The up to four different contributions to the spectra appearing in a narrow range of frequencies (about 10 ppm) and the many parameters required to fit the signals corresponding to quadrupolar ²⁷Al nuclei hindered any attempt of simulation and quantification of the different Al environments. For these reasons, the interpretation of the peaks will be based on a qualitative analysis. In general terms, all the signals corresponding to the different Al environments in TiO₂ rutile increase with increasing the synthesis pressure. This indicates that the global solubility of Al₂O₃ in rutile increases with increasing pressure. However, not all the Al contributions increase in the same proportion.

Signal C is the one whose intensity increases more rapidly with increasing the synthesis pressure. Signals A and B also increase with increasing pressure, but not as much as C. The intensity ratio between signals A and B is very similar in all the spectra indicating a similar increase of both environments with increasing pressure. In the high pressure samples, signal D is only visible in the single pulse MAS spectrum corresponding to the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa, being however the less important contribution to the spectrum. The up to four different octahedral Al environments in Al-doped rutile have been observed at atmospheric pressure, especially in spectra collected at 18.8 T.¹⁴ However the relative intensity of the signals is completely different in the high pressure samples, as it can be inferred from Figure 5. This indicates a different site population of the different Al environments in TiO₂ when increasing the synthesis pressure. The A signal has been assigned to isolated Al in normal octahedral Ti sites of rutile with no adjacent vacancies or interstitial cations.¹⁴ This substitutional Al is actually the clearest contribution to the spectra of the sample synthesised at atmospheric pressure (Figure 5a) but its relative importance is minor at high pressure. The assignation of the other Al signals is not so straightforward and it will be based on the previous XRD analysis and on the data existing in the literature for Al-doped TiO₂ at atmospheric pressure. On one hand, the XRD results strongly suggested the presence of octahedral interstitial aluminium at high pressures. The occupation of this environment increases with increasing the synthesis pressure. On the other hand, it has been reported in the literature that the substitutional mechanism is the most important one for Al-doped rutile at low alumina contents at atmospheric pressure, while the incorporation of Al³⁺ cations into normally unoccupied rutile interstitial sites seems to gain importance at relatively higher Al contents.¹⁵ A clustering of both interstitial and substitutional Al (i.e., an association of one Al³⁺ on a substitutional place and another on a neighbouring interstitial place) has also been observed at high Al content in rutile.^{13, 15} However, theoretical studies indicate that the models based on interstitial Al are less energetically favourable than the models based on substitutional aluminium, although the presence of some interstitial aluminium could also be possible.^{29, 32} Despite interstitial aluminium has also been reported at atmospheric pressure, XRD data show that its importance is much higher at high pressure, producing the change of the rutile symmetry. According to these observations, interstitial Al should be

the one showing a faster increase with increasing pressure. Signal C is the one which increases more rapidly with increasing pressure, being even the most important contribution to the ^{27}Al 3Q-MAS-NMR spectrum of the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa. Thus, this signal should correspond to Al occupying rutile octahedral interstices. Signal B can therefore be assigned to substitutional aluminium associated with interstitial aluminium. This signal appears maybe in the spectrum of the sample synthesised at atmospheric pressure, being however a minor contribution. The position of this signal (B) is also the closest to the one corresponding to the substitutional isolated Al (signal A), being thus the most similar environment to this one.

The position of a NMR signal of a quadrupolar nucleus does not depend only on the chemical environment around the nucleus but also on the quadrupolar interaction. However, the combination of multiple quantum MAS spectra with high external magnetic fields would reduce considerably the quadrupolar coupling. In fact, the position of signal C (i.e., interstitial Al) in the triple quantum MAS spectra does not change appreciably with increasing pressure. Taking into account that this interstitial aluminium would be more distorted than the environments represented by the A and B signals (both corresponding to substitutional Al), the slight changes in the position of both A and B signals should be produced by small changes in the environments around these Al. Considering this assumption, the presence of interstitial aluminium seems to shift the signal corresponding to both the substitutional aluminium environments toward higher frequencies (ppm more positives). On one hand, the original signal corresponding to isolated Al in Ti places (signal A, the clearest contribution to the NMR spectra at atmospheric pressure) would be shifted about 4 ppm toward higher frequencies when associated with a neighbouring interstitial aluminium, becoming signal B in the high pressure samples. On the other hand, in a second level of change, the increase of the population of interstitial aluminium would shift both signals slightly toward higher frequencies.

Thus, the significant presence of interstitial Al in Al-doped rutile samples at high pressure, compared to the samples at atmospheric pressure, would make the Al environment represented by the B signal

(i.e., substitutional aluminium associated with interstitial aluminium) the most important Al environment in Al-doped rutile at relatively lower pressure, when the substitutional mechanism of solubility is still the most important one. The less intense signal D was also observed by Stebbins at atmospheric pressure and was attributed either to Al in octahedral interstices with slightly shorter mean distances, or Al in Ti sites that are in isolated pairs with other Al³⁺ cations.¹⁴ Both the large difference between the D signal position in both single pulse MAS and 3Q MAS spectra and the shape of the crossing signal corresponding to this environment in the MQMAS spectrum (Figure 3II) indicate a highly distorted Al environment with a large quadrupolar coupling. However, high pressure does not seem to have a big effect on this environment.

Tetrahedral aluminium has also been reported as a minor contribution in Al-doped rutile at atmospheric pressure.¹⁴ According to the single pulse MAS spectra, its presence at high pressure is also residual. Thus, high pressure does not seem to have an appreciable effect on this Al environment.

NMR data confirm the presence of octahedral interstitial Al in rutile at high pressure. This contribution also exists on the NMR spectrum of the sample synthesised at 1 GPa, despite its intensity is lower than in the higher pressure samples. This indicates that the increase of the site population corresponding to interstitial octahedral aluminium with increasing the synthesis pressure is the responsible for the change of the rutile symmetry between 1 to 3 GPa at 1300°C.

4. Conclusions

High pressure enhances aluminium solubility in rutile and produces a change in the rutile symmetry, which transform from a tetragonal to an orthorhombic material. Aluminium is incorporated into the rutile structure at high pressures by two mechanisms. The main one consists of the substitution of Ti⁴⁺ by Al³⁺ on normal octahedral sites, compensating the lower positive charge by oxygen vacancies and by the incorporation of Al³⁺ mostly into octahedral interstices of the rutile structure. This last incorporation is induced by high pressure. The existence of an interstitial solid solution at higher pressures provides

the charge balance required to compensate the continuous substitutional solid solution and thus enhances the global Al_2O_3 solubility in rutile. The rutile structure is able to accommodate some octahedral interstitial Al up to a certain limit without changing its symmetry, but the increase of the population of this environment with increasing the synthesis pressure is responsible for the reduction in the rutile symmetry.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT: Dr. María Dolores Alba is gratefully acknowledged for help with the MAS-NMR data interpretation. Supported by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Postdoctoral Fellowship MICINN-FECYT), the Visitors Programme of the Bayerisches Geoinstitut, and the Leibniz program of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (LA 830/14-1 to FL). Two anonymous reviewers are also acknowledged for their valuable comments to the manuscript and their constructive suggestions.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Selected portions of the X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples: a) 99.3% TiO₂ + 0.7% Al₂O₃ calcined at 1500°C; b) 95% TiO₂ + 5% Al₂O₃ synthesised at 1 GPa and 1300°C; c) 95% TiO₂ + 5% Al₂O₃ synthesised at 3 GPa and 1300°C; d) 95% TiO₂ + 5% Al₂O₃ synthesised at 5.5 GPa and 1600°C. * = rutile reflections that split due to the loss of symmetry. X = α -Al₂O₃

Figure 2. XRD pattern of the sample synthesised at 5.5 GPa and 1600°C (black crosses) and the corresponding GSAS calculated pattern using the *Pnmm* space group (continuous red line). The difference plot is also shown. * = rutile reflections that split due to the loss of symmetry.

Figure 3. 3Q-MAS-NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at I) 3 GPa and 1300°C and II) 5.5 GPa and 1600°C.

Figure 4. F1 projections of the 3Q-MAS-NMR spectra of the samples synthesised at a) 3 GPa and 1300°C and b) 5.5 GPa and 1600°C.

Figure 5. Single pulse MAS spectra of the samples synthesised at a) atmospheric pressure and 1500°C; b) 1 GPa and 1300°C; c) 3 GPa and 1300°C and d) 5.5 GPa and 1600°C. A magnification of the spectrum corresponding to the sample synthesised at 3 GPa has been added to the figure. The arrow represents tetrahedral Al. * = spinning side bands.

TABLES.

Table 1. Al-doped rutile unit cell parameters (a, b, c and volume) determined from the Le Bail analysis. Samples synthesised at atmospheric pressure and 1 GPa are tetragonal whereas the synthesised at 3 and 5.5 GPa are orthorhombic.

Sample	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	Volume (Å ³)
0.1 MPa, 1500°C	4.5943		2.9595	62.4679
1 GPa, 1300°C	4.5935		2.9584	62.4229
3 GPa, 1300°C	4.5961	4.5898	2.9586	62.4122
5.5 GPa, 1600°C	4.5567	4.6346	2.9536	62.3755

REFERENCES

- Cheng, H. M.; Ma, J. M.; Zhao, Z. G.; Qi, L. M. *Chem. Mater.* **1995**, *7* (4), 663-671.
- Nowotny, J.; Sorrell, C. C.; Bak, T.; Sheppard, L. R. *Solar Energy* **2005**, *78* (5), 593-602.
- Bahnemann, D. *Solar Energy* **2004**, *77* (5), 445-459.
- Colón, G.; Belver, C.; Fernández-García, M., *Synthesis, properties, and applications of oxide nanomaterials*. John Wiley & Sons: 2007.
- Bingham, S.; Daoud, W. A. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 2041-2050.
- Nikolay, T.; Larina, L.; Shevaleevskiy, O.; Ahn, B. T. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2011**, *4*, 1480-1486.
- Nowotny, M. K.; Sheppard, L. R.; Bak, T.; Nowotny, J. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, *112* (14), 5275-5300.
- Chang, J. C.; Tsai, W. J.; Chiu, T. C.; Liu, C. W.; Chao, J. H.; Lin, C. H. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 4605-4614.
- Feng, N. D.; Zheng, A. M.; Wang, Q. A.; Ren, P. P.; Gao, X. Z.; Liu, S. B.; Shen, Z. R.; Chen, T. H.; Deng, F. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2011**, *115* (6), 2709-2719.
- Ou, H. H.; Lo, S. L.; Liao, C. H. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2011**, *115* (10), 4000-4007.
- Peng, B.; Meng, X. W.; Tang, F. Q.; Ren, X. L.; Chen, D.; Ren, J. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2009**, *113* (47), 20240-20245.
- Liu, G.; Yang, H. G.; Wang, X. W.; Cheng, L. N.; Pan, J.; Lu, G. Q.; Cheng, H. M. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131* (36), 12868-12869.
- Slepetys, R. A.; Vaughan, P. A. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1969**, *73* (7), 2157-2162.
- Stebbins, J. F. *Chem. Mater.* **2007**, *19* (7), 1862-1869.
- Gesenhues, U.; Rentschler, T. *J. Solid State Chem.* **1999**, *143* (2), 210-218.
- Stebbins, J. F.; Farnan, I.; Klabunde, U. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **1989**, *72* (11), 2198-2200.
- Gesenhues, U. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology a-Chemistry* **2001**, *139* (2-3), 243-251.
- McMillan, P. F. *Nat. Mater.* **2002**, *1* (1), 19-25.
- McMillan, P. F. *Chem. Commun.* **2003**, (8), 919-923.
- Zack, T.; Moraes, R.; Kronz, A. *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* **2004**, *148* (4), 471-488.
- Tomkins, H. S.; Powell, R.; Ellis, D. J. *Journal of Metamorphic Geology* **2007**, *25* (6), 703-713.
- Mezger, K.; Hanson, G. N.; Bohlen, S. R. *Earth. Planet. Sci. Lett.* **1989**, *96* (1-2), 106-118.
- Larson, A. C.; Von Dreele, R. B. *GSAS: General Structural Analysis system*, The Regents of the University of California: Los Alamos National Laboratory. Los Alamos, NM, 1994.
- Frydman, L.; Harwood, J. S. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, *117* (19), 5367-5368.
- Medek, A.; Harwood, J. S.; Frydman, L. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, *117* (51), 12779-12787.

26. Amoureux, J. P.; Fernandez, C.; Steuernagel, S. *J. Magn. Reson., Ser A* **1996**, *123* (1), 116-118.
27. Massiot, D. *J. Magn. Reson., Ser A* **1996**, *122* (2), 240-244.
28. Bokhimi, X.; Morales, A.; Pedraza, F. *J. Solid State Chem.* **2002**, *169* (2), 176-181.
29. Steveson, M.; Bredow, T.; Gerson, A. R. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *4* (2), 358-365.
30. Toebbens, D. M.; Stuesser, N.; Knorr, K.; Mayer, H. M.; Lampert, G. *Mater. Sci. Forum* **2001**, *378*, 288-293.
31. Jones, J. B. *Acta Crystallographica Section B-Structural Crystallography and Crystal Chemistry* **1968**, *B 24*, 355-358.
32. Sayle, D. C.; Catlow, C. R. A.; Perrin, M. A.; Nortier, P. *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **1995**, *56* (6), 799-805.

SYNOPSIS TOC

